

Acknowledgement

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Chemical Examination of *Coccinia indica* Fruits

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AS a part of our investigation on the chemical constituents of Indian medicinal plants, we examined the fruits of *Coccinia indica*, a plant known to possess hypoglycemic properties^{1,2}. The phytochemicals earlier reported from the fresh fruits of *C. indica*^{3,4} includes sitosterol, some common triterpenes and a glycoside of cucurbitacin B. Chemical examination of unripe fruits of *C. indica* collected from our University campus yielded taraxerone in addition to previously reported sitosterol and taraxerol from the petroleum ether extract of the plant material and a white crystalline solid (m.p. 282°) from ethyl acetate extract which appeared to be a glycoside of sitosterol rather than that of cucurbitacin B, as evidenced from the m.p. and tlc behaviour of the glycoside and the derived aglycone. But sitosterol is rarely a homogeneous compound and determination of its exact composition and particularly the configuration of the C-24 alkyl function is important as the latter depends on the taxonomy and evolutionary status of the plant⁵. Though it is generally known that (24*R*)-24-ethylcholest-5-en-3 β -ol is dominant in higher plants, it is in no way exclusive. Further, the presence of diastereoisomeric mixture, presumably due to lack of stereochemical control during the biogenesis or epimerisation of a labile biogenetic intermediate, is known⁶. The close physicochemical properties of C-24 epimeric compounds elude their distinction by simple spectroscopic methods and their resolution by conventional chromatographic techniques. ¹³C nmr spectral analysis and, to a limited extent, high resolution ¹H nmr spectral analysis (200 MHz or

above) are regarded as reliable methods for ascertaining the configuration of the C-24 alkyl function and also for good quantitative analysis of common sitosterol constituents^{6,7}. It has been reported⁶ that resonance signals of carbon atoms at 20 and 23–27 positions of 24*R* isomers differ significantly from the corresponding signals of 24*S* isomers. The isolated glycoside was, therefore, acetylated and the ¹³C nmr spectrum of the resulting tetraacetate was studied and the data clearly revealed it to be an acetylglucoside of (24*R*)-24-ethylcholest-5-en-3 β -ol.

Fresh mature fruits of *C. indica* were cut into slices, sun-dried, pulverised (0.6 kg) and extracted successively with petroleum ether, ethyl acetate and 95% ethanol. The concentrated petroleum ether extract on chromatographic resolution over silica gel from petroleum ether eluate furnished taraxerone, m.p. 236°; $\nu_{\max}$ (nujol) 1 710 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃, 80 MHz) 0.83, 0.95, 1.14 (3H, s each), 0.91 (6H, s), 1.07 (9H, s) and 5.6 (1H, dd, *J* 7.8, 3.6 Hz); *m/z* 424 (50), 300 (100), 285 (62), 205 (48), 204 (78), 201 (29), 189 (29), 135 (52) and 107 (58). The benzene eluate furnished in addition to sitosterol (m.p. 135°), a triterpene alcohol, m.p. 276°; [α]_D+4.56° (CHCl₃); *m/z* 426 (31), 411 (20), 302 (100), 287 (57), 204 (97), 189 (23), 135 (53), 121 (40) and 109 (34), which was identified as taraxerol by direct comparison with authentic sample. The ethyl acetate extract on chromatography over silica gel furnished sitosterol glucoside (m.p. 282°) which was proved to be essentially a glucoside of (24*R*)-24-ethylcholest-5-en-3 β -ol from 300 MHz ¹H and 75.5 MHz ¹³C nmr spectral analysis of its tetraacetate (m.p. 152°) prepared by treatment with Ac₂O and pyridine. The resonance signals of the side chain carbons (C-20–C-29) of this tetraacetate were discernible at δ_c 36.1, 18.8, 34.0, 26.2, 45.9, 29.2, 19.1, 19.8, 23.1 and 12.0, in perfect agreement with the reported values⁸.

In spite of the common occurrence of sitosterol glucoside in nature, its isolation is considered important in view of the reported biological activities of its acyl derivatives^{8,9}.

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Ferron as a Spectrophotometric Reagent for Determination of Vanadium(v)

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A large number of spectrophotometric reagents have been reported for the determination of vanadium. Among these, oxine and its derivatives¹⁻⁵ are widely used for the estimation of the element with or without the use of liquid-liquid extraction. Oxinate systems are not very sensitive and thus the sensitivity as well as the selectivity is improved by the substitution of halide, methyl or sulphonic groups at the appropriate positions of 8-hydroxyquinoline. Ferron (7-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid) is found to be the most suitable reagent among the oxine derivatives for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium.

Ferron forms a complex with vanadium(v) extractable into n-butanol⁶. But the recovery of vanadium is not quantitative due to greater solubility of n-butanol in the aqueous phase. Moreover, some of the important elements, tungsten and zirconium interfere seriously in this method and the fate of many elements is not known. The problem of quantitative recovery is overcome by a suitable choice of the solvent having minimum solubility in water. It was reported earlier⁷ that tribenzylamine solution in chloroform could be used for the extraction of vanadium(v)-ferron complex which gives an olive-green extract in the solvent phase.

Accordingly, we present here a more sensitive and selective method for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium after extracting the vanadium(v)-ferron complex into tribenzylamine-chloroform solution.

Experimental

A Perkin-Elmer 550S spectrophotometer equipped with 1 cm matched quartz and silica cells was employed for recording absorption measurements.

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Vanadium(v) stock solution (10 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared from sodium metavanadate, standardised titrimetrically⁸, and diluted to 100 and 10 µg ml⁻¹. Stock solutions of other elements (1-10 mg ml⁻¹) were prepared by dissolving suitable salts in water, or dilute hydrochloric acid. A 1% (w/v) solution of tribenzylamine (TBA) in chloroform was prepared. A 0.15% (w/v) solution of ferron in distilled water was used. Synthetic samples were prepared by mixing solutions of the elements to give the required composition.

Procedure: An aliquot containing $\leq 200\ \mu\text{g}$ o-vanadium(v) was transferred into a 150 ml separatory funnel. Ferron solution (10 ml) and 2 N sulphuric acid (1 ml) were added to it followed by enough distilled water to make the aqueous phase volume to 20 ml. The complex was extracted with tribenzylamine solution (10 ml) in chloroform for 1 min. The two layers were allowed to separate and the solvent phase was drawn into a 25 ml volumetric flask. The extraction was repeated again with TBA-chloroform solution (10 ml). The two extracts were combined and volume was made up to the mark with chloroform. The absorbance of the coloured complex was measured at 390 nm against a reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

Vanadium(v) forms a complex with ferron which is not extracted by benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, methyl isobutyl ketone, isoamyl acetate or ethyl acetate. The complex is extractable with n-butanol⁶ but not recovered 100% even after two extractions. This complex can be extracted quantitatively into TBA-chloroform solution. The absorption spectrum of the olive-green complex of vanadium(v) with ferron in TBA-chloroform solution has been studied. The complex shows a absorption maximum at 390 nm and a small hump in 620-630 nm region. The reagent blank absorbs very strongly at 340 nm which drops sharply to a low value at 370 nm, and beyond it becomes negligibly small. As the complex shows a λ_{max} at 390 nm it is chosen for absorbance measurements.

Effect of variables: The effect of different parameters on the extraction of vanadium(v)-ferron complex is studied. In the study of these variables, 20 ml of aqueous phase containing 5 µg V ml⁻¹ was extracted with equal volume of TBA-chloroform solution and absorbances were measured at 390 nm. On the basis of these studies, the optimum conditions for maximum absorbance are 0.08-0.12 N sulphuric acid, 10-15 ml of 0.1% ferron, 1-2% TBA-chloroform solution and 1-4 min equilibration time.

Beer's law, stability and sensitivity: The olive-green coloured complex of vanadium(v) follows Beer's law up to 10 µg V ml⁻¹ with a Sandell sensitivity of 0.006 µg V cm⁻². The complex is stable for 24 h. Single extraction with 10 ml of 1% TBA-chloroform solutions removes more than 99% of